

Reconfigurable Production Lines for Industrial 5.0 Automation: An Intent-Based Approach

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ABSTRACT Reconfigurable production lines empowered by an intent-based approach and next-generation wireless networks can be a cornerstone of the transformative Industry 5.0 paradigm. This article presents a novel framework for developing an intent-based reconfigurable production line enriched with blockchain technology. By using blockchain as an enabler for decentralization, the proposed approach aims to integrate security and efficiency into the fabric of industrial automation. Experimental evaluations confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach (in terms of scalability and latency) and highlight its strengths and potential for improvement. To be more precise, the blockchain systems are 85 to 95 seconds faster than the cloud service for 50 simultaneous transactions and offer around 69% lower latency at maximum utilization with 10 000 events. Important challenges such as integration into the existing infrastructure, security, standardization and energy efficiency are highlighted and recommendations for overcoming these hurdles are also given at the end of the article.

INDEX TERMS Architecture, industrial automation, intent-based networks, 6G, production lines, blockchain, smart contracts.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the rapidly evolving landscape of industrial automation, the quest for greater flexibility, efficiency and adaptability of production processes has led to a paradigm shift [1]. Traditional manufacturing systems often struggle to adapt quickly to changes in product demand, user-specific requirements or technological advances. Therefore, conventional manufacturing systems, characterized by inflexible and static assembly lines, are being transformed into dynamic systems capable of quickly adapting to changing demands and operational requirements [2]. In contrast to traditional manufacturing systems [3], reconfigurable production lines can offer flexibility

and adaptability in production processes that take into account the dynamics and constant change of modern industrial landscapes and utilize the advantages of reconfigurability [4]. Reconfigurable production lines allow for quick adjustments to different product specifications, production volumes or changes in the production sequence, as they provide flexible and responsive manufacturing systems. Other benefits include reduced downtime during changeovers, increased production efficiency, and the ability to remain competitive in a fast-moving market. This proactive adaptability is particularly important in industries where product lifecycles are short and demand for customization is high [5].

FIGURE 1. Evolution history beginning from the Industry 3.0 to new Industry 4.0 and future Industry 5.0.

A. THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL AUTOMATION

The development of industrial automation has gone through several phases of transformation, reflecting technological progress and a strategic paradigm shift in manufacturing [6]. Fig. 1 shows a general development trend from old Industry 3.0 to new Industry 4.0 and future Industry 5.0. Mechanization began with the Industrial Revolution, when steam-powered machines replaced manual labor. In the subsequent phase of electrification, electricity improved the precision and control of industrial processes. In the mid-20th century, the era of automation began with the introduction of numerical control systems and programmable logic controllers, which streamlined certain tasks and minimized manual intervention. The late 20th century witnessed the integration of computers and ushered in a new era of computerization with Computer Numerical Control systems and Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition systems. The current era, Industry 4.0, is characterized by the convergence of smart technologies, the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Big Data for decentralized decision-making based on real-time analytics. In the 21st century, the industrial paradigm is evolving towards Industry 5.0, focusing on human-machine collaboration, advanced data analytics and integrating new technologies to improve the adaptability and intelligence of production systems. The focus is on integrating human intelligence with intelligent systems and sustainability and social aspects rather than just efficiency and productivity.

B. INTENT-BASED APPROACH AND NEXT-GEN WIRELESS NETWORKS

The transition from Industry 4.0 to Industry 5.0 represents a paradigm shift in manufacturing that is characterized by human-centric automation, improved adaptability and a collaborative relationship between humans and machines. While Industry 4.0 focuses on digitalization and data-driven processes, Industry 5.0 brings added value to production lines through the integration of intelligent decision-making, real-time adaptability and personalization. This development is

particularly important in the context of reconfigurable production lines, where dynamic responses to overarching goals are essential. Modern manufacturing's growing complexity demands more agility and responsiveness than traditional systems can provide. Intent-based approaches meet this need by translating high-level business objectives into executable tasks, thus closing the loop between strategy and shopfloor execution. These systems also react in realtime to shifts in demand, production parameters, or resource availability—enhancing resilience in volatile settings. Furthermore, by leveraging next generation wireless (e.g., 6G or private 5G), they achieve the low latency, high reliability, and bandwidth required for truly reconfigurable production lines.

This article focuses specifically on the development of a novel framework that integrates the principles of intent-based networking into industrial automation, thereby enhancing the operational flexibility and scalability of reconfigurable production lines. This approach enables the production line to be dynamically aligned with business intents, ensuring optimal performance in complex and evolving manufacturing environments aligned with higher-level objectives in next-generation wireless networks [7]. We also explore the potential, challenges and implications of using intent-based strategies in developing and operating reconfigurable production lines.

C. NOVELTY OF THE CONTRIBUTION

While prior efforts have explored intent-based networking in enterprise or telco domains and blockchain for supply chain or access control, our work uniquely merges these two paradigms within the context of reconfigurable industrial production lines for Industry 5.0. Existing frameworks do not address how intents can be securely enforced, transparently executed, and dynamically reconfigured in real-time across factory systems. Our use of blockchain not only secures the intent lifecycle but also supports scalable and distributed automation via smart contracts. Furthermore, our system is experimentally validated to outperform cloud-based implementations in terms of latency, scalability, and robustness

under DDoS threats, which, to our knowledge, has not been demonstrated in previous literature. Our proposed framework offers the following distinct contributions:

- This study pioneers the merging of intent-based approaches with blockchain, leveraging the decentralized and immutable nature of blockchain to improve the propagation and execution of intent with high integrity and transparency.
- The framework supports the dynamic reconfiguration of production lines by enabling real-time, intent-driven adjustments while maintaining operational visibility and security, even as systems scale.
- The use of smart contracts ensures that the business logic underlying intent-based operations remains transparent to all stakeholders, overcoming the “opaque” nature of many automation systems. Smart contracts also enhance system availability and mitigate the impact of DDoS attacks—an aspect often neglected in prior solutions
- We go beyond conceptual proposals by implementing the framework using Hyperledger Fabric. Performance is benchmarked against cloud-based solutions, demonstrating up to 69% lower latency and 85–95 seconds faster batch completion under scaled conditions. This level of validation is absent in comparable studies.
- The framework fosters collaborative environments by combining human-centered, intent-driven automation with distributed decision-making, enabling seamless collaboration between human workers and automated systems.

The above contributions collectively represent a significant advance over existing intent-based and blockchain solutions as they address the unique requirements of Industry 5.0, such as the need for flexibility, human-centered design and secure, distributed decision-making.

II. ARCHITECTURE TRENDS FOR INDUSTRIAL AUTOMATION

A. THE ROAD TO THE INDUSTRIAL 5.0 AUTOMATION

Creating seamless connectivity throughout the factory and eliminating isolated islands of connectivity at the factory floor level is critical in Industry 4.0, as shown in the centre of Fig. 1. Industry 5.0 is still evolving and in its early stages, but it aims to build on the foundations of Industry 4.0, which focused on integrating digital technologies for automation, and introduce new technologies that can further transform the industry [8]. Industry 5.0 marks the next phase in the evolution of industrial automation, emphasising a human-centric approach to manufacturing processes and encouraging greater collaboration between human workers and intelligent machines. This paradigm shift is leading to a more holistic and flexible production environment, where humans and machines coexist and leverage each other’s strengths [9].

Traditional production lines, while common, lack flexibility and struggle to adapt to changing product requirements. They

are typically optimized for fixed tasks, making reconfiguration laborious and downtime-prone. Their isolated components limit integration and real-time data sharing, reducing responsiveness and efficiency [10]. As market demands evolve, this rigidity becomes a critical barrier. Modern manufacturing systems must offer modularity, interoperability, and agility to adapt quickly to changes. These features—supported by AI-driven decision-making—enable better resource utilization, lower downtime, and more responsive operations [11], [12]. Addressing these limitations is essential for transitioning toward reconfigurable production lines with enhanced adaptability and competitiveness [13].

B. CLOUD COMPUTING FOR MANUFACTURING SYSTEMS

Cloud computing is a game-changer technology that leverages the enhanced capabilities of data processing and storage to integrate such services into consumer-facing applications. In manufacturing systems, integrating cloud computing with cyber-physical systems enables the leveraging of manufacturing processes with encapsulated distributed resources deployed in a cloud infrastructure, utilising a pay-as-you-go model [14]. In cloud manufacturing, service-based architecture offers enterprises a promising platform for greater agility [3]. However, cloud-based manufacturing systems are vulnerable to several security threats, inherent to IoT systems.

C. BLOCKCHAIN AS A SUPPORTING TECHNOLOGY

Blockchain has established itself as a decentralized service in manufacturing in recent works [15]. Moreover, [16] provide a systematic review of blockchain innovations in smart, sustainable manufacturing—highlighting green production, resource optimization, and end-to-end traceability. The key benefits of blockchain for Industry 5.0 are improved security and efficiency. Blockchain improves integrity and availability, which are fundamental security requirements for industrial systems. In addition, blockchain facilitates industrial services with decentralized smart contracts to provide service functions with lower latency compared to the cloud. For example, Hewa et al. [17] emphasized the advantages of latency to dynamically deliver authentication and end-to-end encryption using smart contracts for cloud manufacturing. Xu [18] et al. proposed blockchain-based solution which is limited to the identity management for manufacturing applications. Kramer et al. [19] proposed Ethereum blockchain-based production supply chain solution for manufacturing, which sums up the security advantages of blockchain with extensive latency trade off. The events triggered by the smart contracts are subject to consensus-driven approval, which enables robustness against adversarial manipulation compared to centralized service instances. The events approved by consensus are preserved with cryptographic integrity and distributed as blocked batches to form a cryptographically integrity-preserved chain called a *Blockchain*. The events in each block and the chain of blocks are ordered chronologically in the blockchain. In addition, smart contracts provide a robust platform for defining access

FIGURE 2. Characteristics, advantages and challenges of the blockchain-enabled intent-based industrial automation.

control rules to determine conditional access at the business service level, preventing vulnerability to DoS attacks.

In Industry 5.0, *blockchain* is intended to enhance security and transparency in supply chains, transactions, and data exchange. Smart contracts enabled by blockchain will automate and enforce agreements, reducing the need for intermediaries and streamlining processes. *Extended Reality (XR) in Industry 5.0* can revolutionize maintenance, training and collaboration [20]. Workers can use AR to access real-time information, instructions and visualizations while performing tasks. This technology improves situational awareness, reduces errors and improves efficiency. *Improved connectivity through B5G/6G* will enable faster and more reliable data exchange, enabling real-time monitoring, control and collaboration in Industry 5.0. This is critical for autonomous systems, remote control and connected industrial ecosystems. *AI* to optimize decision-making processes is an important prerequisite for developing automation solutions for industry that are mainly guided by intents. Finally, *advanced IoT devices* with enhanced sensing capabilities and embedded intelligence will help create a more responsive and adaptive industrial environment. These devices will enable data-driven insights, predictive maintenance and improved overall efficiency. Fig. 2 illustrates the benefits and challenges associated with blockchain-enabled intent-based reconfigurable production lines. The benefits include immutability for secure data integrity, end-to-end visibility for transparency, dissemination of intents for seamless coordination, increased data security, and distributed decision making enabled by the decentralized nature of blockchain. On the other hand, there are challenges such as high energy consumption due to the computational requirements of blockchain, scalability issues as production systems grow and complex integration into existing industrial systems. These aspects illustrate both the potential and the difficulties of implementing blockchain-supported industrial automation.

III. NEXT-GENERATION INTENT-BASED INFRASTRUCTURE FOR INDUSTRIAL AUTOMATION

A. INTEGRATION OF THE INTENT LAYER

Intent layer represents a set of specific policy types articulated in high-level operational and business objectives [21]. The concept of “intent” has been widely used in the telecommunications industry [22]. The evolution from policy to intent was motivated by the challenges associated with policy management as various entities (e.g., end users without technical understanding, app developers creating network services without extensive network interface expertise, and operators seeking a more abstract and robust initiation of network services) seek simpler solutions. Intents, which humans primarily create, must be transformed into device-consumable or lower-level forms [23], perhaps through generative AI [24]. The basic concept behind intent-based technologies is to fulfill system requirements without getting into the details of how to achieve those goals—considering the advanced integration of intent-based technology into industrial automation systems, a three-layer architecture can be designed, as shown in Fig. 3. This figure shows a blockchain-enabled intent-based framework for Industry 5.0 automation and illustrates the interaction between business intents, the intent layer and the factory floor, supported by modern communication technologies such as 6G and edge cloud infrastructure.

B. OVERVIEW OF THE PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

The primary objective of this architectural framework is to introduce intent-based automation that unlocks capabilities previously unattainable by traditional human workforces. The business intents are high-level goals such as order management, cost optimization and tracking market trends. These are inputs into the intent layer and control the system’s operation. These intents are translated into requests and dynamic updates within the intent layer and form the backbone for actionable tasks. At the business service layer, the intents are derived from Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and include specific Service Level Agreements (SLAs), processes, goals and targets triggered by users at the business layer. The goal of the intention layer is not simply to blindly execute a pre-planned sequence of actions, but to re-evaluate and re-plan after each step. Proactively planned actions are approved within this layer. The blockchain service layer ensures transparency, security and integrity of business intents. The blockchain services have been integrated with the Application Programming Interface (API) endpoints for the security service requests within the production lifecycle. By leveraging the decentralisation features of blockchain, security functions can be flexibly deployed as microservices at the edge or in the cloud to reduce latency while preserving integrity using the cryptographic decentralised ledger. This includes a distributed ledger to store records of intents, updates and actions securely, and smart contracts to automate the execution of tasks once predefined conditions are met, ensuring trust and efficiency. Additionally, we utilise smart contracts to define access

FIGURE 3. An illustrative blockchain-enabled intent-based architecture for industrial automation with next-generation wireless networks.

control rules, thereby protecting the business services layer from DoS attacks. In particular, the immutable ledger contains the conditional restrictions on the use of business services that are validated with the smart contracts when processing requests from the business services layer. This protects the service layer from DoS attackers who intentionally make resource-excessive service calls. The consensus-based event approval process decentralises the power of event inclusion to the ledger while minimising the risk of attackers committing malicious acts within the production lifecycle.

The intent layer depicted in Fig. 3, acts as the decision-making hub, which is executes dynamic updates to adapt operations in response to real-time changes. The results of this layer are sent as actions to the semantic communication agents for implementation. The component *Knowledge* manages the abstraction of intents and provides reasoning by establishing relations between objects while integrating insights and data for optimal task execution. The *Agent* serves as an interface to network objects and executes actions after evaluating the intents to generate actionable tasks based on high-level intents. Although it has no intelligence, the *Agent* requests reasoning from *Knowledge* when an action is required. *Data* observes network objects and facilitates efficient storage by managing information about the network topology and inventory. Dynamic updates triggered by events such as the deployment or de-installation of objects or topology changes are forwarded from *Data* to *Knowledge*. *Data* models the network topology and transfers it to the *Agent*. In particular, *Data* plays a central role in adapting to changing goals and updating the model with more accurate evaluations or changing business intents.

The physical nodes or objects are at the bottom of the network layer in Fig. 3. This layer converts network data into a

formal representation, enabling seamless interaction with the intent layer. It contains the abstract model of the hardware responsible for executing the actions requested by the *Agent*. Some of the expected key technologies are as follows: *Reconfigurable production lines*, a hallmark of Industrial 5.0, enable dynamic changes in manufacturing setups, allowing for swift adaptation to varying product demands and market trends. *Quantum computing*, on the other hand, represents a paradigm shift in data processing and has the potential to revolutionize data analysis, optimization and simulation processes in industry [25]. It can significantly accelerate problem-solving and decision-making, especially in complex industrial automation scenarios. *Semantic communication agents* interface between the intent layer and physical systems and *digital twins* provide virtual replicas of physical systems, allowing real-time monitoring and predictive analytics. The incorporation of blockchain ensures the proposed system’s integrity, accountability, availability, and transparency, utilizing the core features.

C. ARCHITECTURAL ACHIEVEMENTS

The proposed architecture enables reconfigurable production lines to eliminate the static and non-customizable production systems while ensuring security in modern intent-based networks that leverage the potential of blockchain-based smart contracts as indicated in Fig. 3. The intent layer is encoded as smart contracts to ensure robustness against attackers manipulating the policies and underlying intents, a potential security risk in modern systems. From the application perspective of intent for industrial automation, blockchain integration brings several significant benefits to improve *security and efficiency* beyond the state of the art. The main benefits are as follows:

1) TRANSPARENCY IN INTENT EXECUTION TO IMPROVE SECURITY

Blockchain-based smart contracts are transparent and consistent decentralized services that execute computer programs. The decisive advantage is the transparency and consistency of smart contracts compared to the black box of centralized services. In contrast, the stakeholders of centralized event intent-driven execution services are unaware when the attackers compromise the service and deviate from the intended functions. The execution of smart contracts is transparent, and the consensus mechanism with a blockchain approves the successive events and actions-integrated distributed ledger, which provides more transparency to ensure the security in the intent-based services [26].

2) DECENTRALIZATION AND ROBUSTNESS TO THE DOS ATTACKS TO ENSURE AVAILABILITY

The integration of blockchain-based smart contracts for the decentralization of intent-based services ensures the availability of services in multiple instances where, the decentralized architecture ensures the availability of services through decentralization [27].

3) LOWER LATENCY

The decentralized nature of blockchain-based smart contracts shifts services from the cloud to the edge, eliminating the latency during internet transit for intent-based request processing. In contrast, blockchain-based architecture supports connectivity for local and real-time request processing. For example, a large manufacturing shop floor with local 5G operator connectivity would be ideal.

4) IMPROVED SCALABILITY

The decentralized nature of blockchain-based smart contracts eliminates the centralized performance bottleneck in cloud services. Decentralization increases scalability and thus improves the system’s ability to process requests simultaneously [28].

D. WORKFLOWS FOR BUSINESS INTENTS AND SECURITY ANALYSIS

The architecture developed for the management of reconfigurable production lines is divided into three interconnected layers, each of which plays a specific role in ensuring the dynamic adaptability and optimization of production processes, as shown in Fig. 4. At the business level, the primary focus is capturing and synthesizing business requirements from various stakeholders, developing high-level business objectives that align with organizational goals, and developing strategies to expand product production while minimizing costs. With the intent layer, the architecture aims to translate these high-level business goals into actionable, low-level intents tailored to different technologies. This includes summarizing and analyzing business objectives, collecting real-time observations from the production infrastructure and formulating specific

FIGURE 4. The workflow for the completion of business requirements to the execution of device level intents.

FIGURE 5. Implementation setup with the Hyperledger Fabric blockchain platform as a blockchain service.

intents that address different technologies and communication protocols. The intent layer acts as an intermediary, forming an interface to the semantic communication agents to facilitate bidirectional communication between the layers. Finally, the infrastructure layer implements low-level intents and dynamically adapts the production line to the intent requirements. These include decoding semantics, updating digital twins to reflect the current state of production units, changing the production path on the shop floor, using secure M2M quantum communication, recording critical data in a blockchain, analyzing the use of radio resources at the network edge and activating holographic MIMO channels for improved communication and coordination. The seamless interaction between these layers ensures that the overall business objectives are translated into practical and efficient adjustments within the reconfigurable production line. At the same time, Table 1 summarizes the security analysis in the blockchain-enabled intent layer.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The experimental setup was implemented using the Hyperledger Fabric blockchain platform as a blockchain service as indicated in Fig. 5. The integration with mobile network operators and local 5G operators was simulated using the

TABLE 1. Security Analysis in the Blockchain-Enabled Intent Layer

Security Aspect	Description
Integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Digital signatures, a fundamental blockchain feature, are used to ensure integrity. – The blockchain-enabled intent layer secures the integrity of aggregated business goals, high-level intents, observations, low-level intents, and actions for semantic communication agents. – Each element is transformed into transactions, verified by multiple nodes, and included in the blockchain. – Manipulation of integrity requires two conditions: dominance of the consensus and solving cryptographic challenges like the ECDLP.
Accountability for Non-repudiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The blockchain-enabled intent layer preserves accountability and non-repudiation by managing business workflows as transactions. – These transactions are stored in blocks in chronological order after consensus approval. – Tampering with records requires domination of the consensus and solving cryptographic challenges like ECDLP. – The architecture ensures accountability through its robust consensus mechanism.
Availability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The decentralized nature of blockchain ensures availability by providing multiple instances of the blockchain-enabled intent layer, avoiding single points of failure. – It also offers resilience against DoS attacks while maintaining transaction processing scalability.
Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Blockchain facilitates transparency in collaborative environments by using distributed smart contracts to define business logic. – This ensures transparency in the aggregation of business goals, the generation of high-level intents, processing low-level intents, and sending actions to semantic communication agents, avoiding the opacity of a black-box system.
Scalability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Blockchain’s architecture can be adapted to handle growing transaction volumes through mechanisms such as sharding, off-chain solutions, and improved consensus algorithms. – Scalability is maintained by allowing parallel transaction processing while ensuring security and integrity are not compromised.

REST API with the Hyperledger Fabric Software Development Kit for calling blockchain-based functions accordingly. The intents were encoded as smart contracts, also known as chaincode in Java programming language. We converted the intents into programmatic functions and deployed them as smart contracts in the Hyperledger Fabric blockchain environment. The APIs also operate as integration endpoints with the factory floor shops. For the experimental evaluation, we generated the factory floor and mobile operator events programmatically. We used software programs with multiple threads to increase the number of concurrent transactions. The comparison results of the proposal is done compared to the cloud-based manufacturing architecture [3]. We have investigated the integration of intent events into the blockchain. We have programmatically simulated the intent events and evaluated the latency and scalability. To see the benefits of the proposed work, we partially reimplemented the baseline system using identical inputs for both the baseline and our proposed approach. All the related services were deployed as micro-services, using Docker containers to simulate production-grade deployment setup.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed blockchain-enabled intent-based framework for reconfigurable production lines and capture the framework’s ability to operate efficiently, securely, and responsively in dynamic industrial environments, we consider the following key metrics: **(i) Latency:** Measured as the average time required to access or process intent events from the distributed ledger. **(ii) Scalability:** Assessed by evaluating the system’s batch completion time under varying levels of concurrent transactions. **(iii) Security and Availability:** Evaluated through simulations of DDoS attack scenarios, where the system’s ability to maintain service performance under increasing malicious request load is measured.

A. INTENT EVENT ACCESS LATENCY EVALUATION

The business processes in the production lifecycle involve multiple steps that access the intent events to retrieve and verify data. Therefore, we evaluated the latency in accessing the intent data, which is very important for the entire business

FIGURE 6. Average latency in retrieving intent events compared to the number of intent events registered in the system.

process lifecycle. The data requires concurrent and dynamic access to update observations and perform actions in the intent layer as shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 6 evaluates the access latency of intent layer data stored in the distributed ledger. The cloud-based system exhibits significantly higher latency compared to the proposed system, with latency steadily increasing as the number of registered events increases. At low load, i.e., with approximately 1,000 registered events, the cloud-based system has an average latency of about 72 ms, while the proposed system achieves a much lower latency of 18 ms, which is 54 ms faster, i.e., about 75% lower latency. At a moderate load of approximately 5,000 events, the latency of the cloud-based system increases to about 77 ms, whereas it is 22 ms for the proposed system, resulting in a 55 ms advantage and a 71% lower latency. At maximum utilisation with 10,000 events, the cloud-based system achieves 80 ms, while the latency of the proposed system remains at a significantly lower 25 ms, corresponding to a performance improvement of 55 ms, or approximately 69% lower latency. The trend in Fig. 6 shows that the cloud-based system experiences a significant increase in latency as the number of events grows, demonstrating the limits of scalability. Our implementation outperforms the latency in accessing the intent data from the

FIGURE 7. Batch completion time versus number of concurrent transactions per batch for scalability within a cloud-based system (Extrapolated for 75 and 100).

ledger compared to the state of the art in cloud-based scenarios, indicating better efficiency and scalability in processing large workloads. Lower access latency can improve the overall production process efficiency while eliminating the risk of a single point of failure. This suggests that the proposed system is more suitable for real-time applications, such as industrial automation and IoT networks, where low latency and high scalability are critical.

B. SCALABILITY EVALUATION

The proposed system is envisioned to support scalability, as the production life cycle involves a large number of intent event request processing. Hence, we evaluated the scalability of the proposed approach by invoking the system with concurrent transactions in batches of different sizes using multi-threaded software programs, as shown in Fig. 7. For each batch size, we performed 100 trials and recorded the mean batch completion latency. First, we partially implemented a cloud-based system and provided the same input to simulate the intent-based scenario of a centralized manufacturing system and our proposal. We configured the block mining parameter of the Hyperledger Fabric blockchain in 0.5 s, 1 s, and 2 s to evaluate the average end-to-end transaction completion latency times of the batches. The approach proposed in this article decentralizes the services and thus offers more scalability than the centralized systems. As can be seen in Fig. 7, our work provides a latency advantage in scaled scenarios as the decentralized approach removes the performance bottleneck. The batch completion time for the cloud service increases significantly as the number of concurrent transactions grows, indicating potential scalability challenges due to centralization and processing bottlenecks. At 10 concurrent transactions, the cloud service takes approximately 30 seconds, which escalates to 110 seconds at 50 concurrent transactions, indicating scalability limitations.

In contrast, blockchain systems have significantly lower and more stable batch completion times, with performance depending on the block mining time. The blockchain system with a block mining time of 0.5 s performs best. It completes a batch of 10 transactions in approximately 15 seconds and 50 transactions in about 25 seconds and shows only a minimal increase despite the higher load. The system with a block mining time of 1 s completes 10 transactions in 17 seconds and 50 transactions in 30 seconds, while the system with a block mining time of 2 s has slightly higher times of 20 seconds for 10 transactions and 35 seconds for 50 transactions. Even the slowest blockchain system outperforms the cloud service by far. With 50 concurrent transactions, for example, blockchain systems are 85 to 95 seconds faster than cloud services. At the same time, blockchain systems demonstrate significantly better scalability than cloud services, even at higher block mining times (e.g., 2 seconds). The increase in completion time remains linear and is less steep when the number of concurrent transactions increases. Lower block mining times (e.g. 0.5 s) result in slightly better performance, especially when the transaction load increases. This shows how important it is to optimize mining times for better real-time performance.

$$T_c^{(r)} = T_c^{(n)} + \frac{T_c^{(n)} - T_c^{(n-1)}}{N^{(n)} - N^{(n-1)}} \cdot (N^{(r)} - N^{(n)}) \quad (1)$$

In the experiment, we found that memory constraints limit the scaling of transactions to 50. We used linear extrapolation, as given in (1), to estimate the latency at transaction counts of 75 and 100. The results indicate that blockchain systems with optimized block mining times (e.g. 0.5 s or 1 s) can achieve low-latency responses. In scenarios such as real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and distributed decision-making, this ensures consistent and reliable performance.

Since we propose a consortium-based approach, it is possible to agree with the consortium members on a block mining time based on the number of concurrent requests, which corresponds to the scale of the production system. In large industrial environments with numerous simultaneous operations, the blockchain-enabled system can have better scalability than traditional centralized solutions such as cloud services. This is crucial for environments such as smart factories, where hundreds or thousands of devices and systems interact simultaneously. The decentralized nature of the blockchain reduces dependence on a central server and thus minimizes the risks of bottlenecks or single points of failure. This makes the system more resilient, especially in critical applications such as industrial robotics, assembly lines and supply chain management. The linear growth in batch completion times for blockchain systems indicates that they can handle dynamically changing workloads without drastic performance degradation. This adaptability is essential in environments such as Industry 5.0, where human-robot collaboration and on-demand reconfiguration are key requirements.

FIGURE 8. End-to-end service completion latency under varying levels of DDoS attacks.

C. DDOS ATTACK ROBUSTNESS EVALUATION

Robustness against DDoS attacks is a crucial consideration for ensuring system availability. Especially if the security services exist as a single instance, DDoS attackers can easily attack the security services and gain access to the system, putting the entire system at massive risk. In our work, we propose to integrate decentralized access control verification with blockchain-based smart contracts. Specifically, we define the boundaries of access requirements in the form of an individualized profile and encode in the smart contracts. Each time the service is invoked, the smart contract verifies the profile information and authorizes or denies access to the system. We evaluated the robustness against DDoS attacks using programmatically simulated DDoS requests and evaluated the end-to-end response time of the intent service for the non-adversarial requests. We assume that the minimal impact on end-to-end latency for intent service requests to non-adversarial nodes indicates that the system is robust to DDoS attacks and ensures availability.

Fig. 8 illustrates the average service completion latency (in milliseconds) as a function of the number of malicious business service invocation requests per legitimate request. Fig. 8 compares four scenarios: (1) without blockchain-based access control verification, (2) with blockchain-based verification at different block times—0.5 s, 1 s, and 2 s. The results show that the absence of blockchain-based verification leads to significantly higher latencies, particularly as the number of malicious requests increases. Therefore, blockchain-based profile verification increases system latency but ensures availability when malicious requests to invoke business services increase. If there are no malicious requests, the latency time for the system without blockchain verification is approximately 3,500 ms, which is slightly higher than that of the blockchain-verified system with a block time of 0.5 s (~3,000 ms). With longer block times (e.g. 2 s), however, the latency increases slightly to ~3,600 ms, which indicates that shorter block times offer better baseline performance. When the malicious activity increases to 20 malicious requests,

the latency for the system without verification doubles to 7,000 ms, while blockchain-verified systems have much lower latencies, ranging from 3,500 ms (BlockTime = 0.5 s) to 5,000 ms (BlockTime = 2 s). At the highest number of malicious requests (50 malicious requests), the latency for the system without blockchain verification increases to 13,000 ms, more than three times the latency of the best-performing blockchain-verified system with a block time of 0.5 s (4,000 ms). The difference between shorter and longer block times becomes even more pronounced with higher malicious load, where BlockTime = 2 s has 2,500 ms higher latency than BlockTime = 0.5 s.

V. CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. KEY CHALLENGES

The key challenges in enabling reconfigurable production lines for industrial automation in the context of Industry 5.0 and in-depth discussion on these topics include:

- *Integration with Existing Infrastructure:* A major barrier to deploying blockchain-enabled intent-based reconfigurable production lines is the integration with existing manufacturing infrastructure [31]. Many factories still rely on legacy Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs), fixed-function automation, and proprietary interfaces that lack support for dynamic reconfiguration and semantic communication. Retrofitting these systems requires upgrading to programmable edge devices and modifying SCADA (Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition) and MES (Manufacturing Execution Systems) layers to interpret high-level intents—changes that risk downtime and operational disruption. Cost is another concern: infrastructure overhaul demands investment in blockchain-capable nodes, edge computing, and advanced connectivity (e.g., 6G), with ongoing maintenance and compliance costs. Proprietary system vendors may resist integration, and stakeholders may distrust decentralized governance. Additionally, increased autonomy and opaque AI models used for intent translation raise concerns over safety, accountability, and bias, especially in critical decision-making scenarios.
- *Security and Privacy:* Security and privacy are major challenges in blockchain-enabled intent-based production lines, especially when third-party vendor equipment is involved [32]. Post-quantum cryptography can help mitigate threats from emerging quantum attacks [33], [34]. Industrial systems increasingly depend on remote access for diagnostics and updates, which—if poorly secured—can be exploited to inject malicious code or manipulate smart contracts. Unlike centralized systems shielded by internal firewalls, decentralized architectures broaden the threat surface, especially in multi-vendor or consortium-based deployments. A compromised supplier node, for instance, could alter smart contracts, disable access controls, or disrupt operations across sites. This is particularly critical in regulated industries

TABLE 2. Comparison of Different Production Lines and Proposal for the Development Towards Industry 5.0 Automation in Terms of Their Characteristics, Advantages and Limitations

Technology	Characteristics	Advantages	Limitations
Traditional Assembly Production Lines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sequential arrangement of workstations – Specialized tasks at each station – Fixed workstations dedicated to specific tasks. – Products move along a conveyor belt 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High efficiency for large-scale production. – Lower per-unit production costs. – Predictable production outputs . – Time-tested manufacturing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –Rigid and difficult to adapt to changes – Requires significant initial capital investment – Long changeover times – Struggles with product design variations
Flexible Manufacturing Systems [29]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Highly automated production – Centralized computer control — Designed to accommodate changes in the production process, allowing for customization and adaptation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – More productive than traditional production lines – Adaptation and customization capabilities. – Integrated quality control for higher quality. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – More expensive than traditional production lines – Requires regular maintenance – Complex design, operation, and maintenance
Automated Manufacturing Systems [30]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Utilizes automation, robotics, and machinery. – Modular units for specific tasks. – User-friendly interface for process control. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Higher precision and speed – Continuous and consistent production – High level of accuracy and repeatability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – High initial investment – Complex maintenance and repair – Difficult to adapt to unexpected changes
Cloud-integrated Manufacturing systems [3]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Incorporates cloud computing manufacturing in remote locations – Enables cross-border manufacturing – Production data transfers over the internet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Reduces carbon footprint of logistics –Reduces lead time –Ensures brand integrity –Preserves intellectual property 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Suffers from the security threats from communication. – Lack of control in production processes –Challenges of scalability
Proposed blockchain enabled Intent-based Reconfigurable Production Lines for Industry 5.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Blockchain for immutability and transparency – Smart contracts for automated adjustments. – End-to-end visibility and traceability – Disseminate intents with decentralized blockchain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Semantic resource consumption – Distributed decision-making aligned with intents — Increased data security and reduced cyber risks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Scalability challenges in dynamic environments – High energy consumption of blockchain actions – Complex integration with existing systems

like aerospace or pharmaceuticals, where integrity is non-negotiable. Additionally, persistent monitoring for predictive analytics may raise concerns over surveillance and autonomy. Securing such decentralized systems incurs substantial costs, including investments in encryption, identity management, secure edge bootstrapping, intrusion detection, and continuous compliance auditing.

- **Standardization and Interoperability:** Standardization and interoperability remain major obstacles to adopting blockchain-enabled intent-based production systems in Industry 5.0 [35]. Industrial setups often involve heterogeneous equipment with proprietary protocols, leading to fragmented technology silos that hinder unified intent translation. Integrating these systems requires custom middleware, semantic translation engines, or protocol adapters (e.g., for OPC-UA, Modbus, or Ethernet/IP), increasing both complexity and potential points of failure. Even with such solutions, ensuring consistent interpretation of high-level intents (e.g., “optimize energy use”) across diverse machines is difficult. Moreover, firmware updates and reconfigurations demand ongoing maintenance of integration layers, adding to lifecycle costs and operational risk.
- **Energy Efficiency:** The significant energy consumption of 6G devices and systems in large-scale manufacturing settings, further complicated by the added energy demands of implementing a blockchain-enabled system, which may require substantial computational

resources and power for processing and maintaining the blockchain network could be a significant challenge [36]. For example, a large automotive plant using blockchain-based systems to monitor production could see a significant increase in energy consumption, especially during peak operating hours. This could require investment in renewable energy sources or energy storage systems to offset the increased demand, driving up implementation costs.

- **Blockchain-based Challenges:** Although blockchain brings integrity and decentralization, it can suffer from limited transaction throughput and higher consensus latency presents various approaches to production lines, highlighting their characteristics, advantages, and substantial energy. These challenges may incur additional latency and energy consumption trade-off in the production lines. Especially, when the blockchain-based services are hosted in the edge layer of a large-scale production line with limited computational and memory resources, the resources will easily overflow and hinder the services that rely on the blockchain. To mitigate these issues, adopting permissioned/consortium ledgers with efficient consensus (e.g. Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT) or Proof of Stake (PoS)), Layer2 statechannel or sharding techniques are recommended for higher throughput, and offchain processing for noncritical data. Deploying energyaware hardware and integrating renewable power sources further reduces

the environmental footprint. Furthermore, research and development of optimal consensus algorithms instead of relying on the state of the art will add extensive value to leverage the advancement of blockchain for factory automation with minimised inherent limitations of blockchain.

B. RECOMMENDATIONS

Overcoming the challenges of using blockchain-enabled intent-based reconfigurable production lines in industry requires a multi-layered approach. For the seamless integration of technologies, collaboration with specialized providers is crucial to foster partnerships that enable smooth technological convergence. Standardizing protocols ensures interoperability between the various components of the production line, while robust security measures and compliance frameworks protect the sensitive data stored in the blockchain. Addressing skills gaps (particularly about blockchain and the latest generative AI-enabled techniques for intent management) requires comprehensive training programs that enable employees to use these new technologies effectively. Change management strategies applied to industrial processes and supported by effective communication can help organizations understand the benefits of the transition. A thorough cost-benefit analysis highlights the long-term benefits, emphasizing improved productivity and reduced operating costs. Compliance with ever-evolving regulations and collaboration with regulators ensures compliance and legal alignment. Table 2 provides different approaches to production lines in terms of their characteristics, advantages and limitations. Specifically, we recommend for hybrid onchain/offchain architectures and permissioned chains with tuneable block times to balance latency vs. security, plus the use of green consensus algorithms and renewablebacked nodes to curb energy costs.

We also recommend embedding sustainability into reconfigurable production lines through three complementary measures: (1) deploying renewable-powered edge nodes—e.g. onsite solar or wind installations—to underwrite local blockchain validation and reduce reliance on fossil-fueled grid power; (2) implementing energyaware intent scheduling that defers nonurgent reconfiguration tasks to offpeak periods, smoothing demand peaks and lowering energy costs; and (3) adopting green consensus mechanisms—transitioning from PoW to PoS or hybrid PoS/PoA protocols—to slash computational overhead without compromising security. For instance, pilot blockchain-enabled supply-chain projects have demonstrated 8–12% emission reductions through traceability and renewable integration [37].

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

This article presents a pioneering framework for the development and deployment of intent-based reconfigurable production lines in the context of Industry 5.0. By utilizing an intent-based approach and integrating blockchain technology, the proposed infrastructure provides a transformative solution to the challenges faced by traditional production

lines. The proposed framework has been implemented and evaluated using Hyperledger Fabric, providing empirical evidence of its technical feasibility and performance advantages in latency, scalability, and security. Specifically, our implementation demonstrated that the proposed blockchain-enabled intent-based system outperforms traditional cloud-based manufacturing systems across multiple performance metrics. It achieved up to 69% lower latency when handling 10,000 concurrent intent events and 85–95 seconds faster batch completion times for 50 concurrent transactions. The architecture also proved robust against DDoS attacks, maintaining low latency under adversarial conditions when equipped with blockchain-based access control. These experimental outcomes validate the suitability of the proposed framework for scalable, secure, and real-time industrial automation settings envisioned in Industry 5.0. However, key challenges such as integration into existing infrastructure, security and privacy concerns, standardization and interoperability issues, and energy efficiency considerations remain significant hurdles.

Future research should focus on enhancing the operational readiness of intent-based reconfigurable production lines, especially in live industrial settings. A top priority is improving energy efficiency through greener computing methods, renewable integration, and energy-aware consensus protocols like PoS. Exploring advanced mechanisms such as delegated Proof of Stake (dPoS), Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT), and quantum-safe cryptography can further boost scalability and resilience. Strengthening security and privacy will require zero-knowledge proofs and layered defense architectures with real-time anomaly detection. Finally, integrating quantum networks and cryptographic tools offers new possibilities for secure, low-latency decision-making.

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